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Postmortem Axial Heat Transfer

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Abstract—A recent study indicated that the axial temperature distribution of a body at death predicts presence/absence of the postmortem temperature plateau (PMTP). This paper studied the relationship between a body's antemortem axial temperature distribution and the PMTP using numerical analysis methods. First, the antemortem axial temperature distribution was numerically approximated in a high anatomical-fidelity 3D human phantom. The Pennes Bioheat Model was applied and tissue blood perfusion and metabolic heat generation parameters were specified. The so-approximated antemortem axial temperature distribution constituted the *initial condition* for a follow-on numerical simulation of postmortem cooling in which the aforementioned tissue parameters were set to zero to simulate death. The simulation demonstrated that the 37°C antemortem central isotherm (ACI) – the 'hot core' – gradually reduced in diameter and disappeared over a period of 3 hours 51 minutes, manifesting as the PMTP when detected by single-point core thermometry. The ratio of the ACI radius to body radius at death, thermometry-depth, body radius and the postmortem interval (PMI) at thermometry were some of the predictors of PMTP length. Their non-quantification during death-time estimation is a source of uncertainty. Continued heat transfer resulted in perpetual formation of consecutive and progressively cooler circumferential isotherms on the skin that gradually propagated towards the body centre and sequentially replaced the ACI. The axial thermal profile thus continuously evolved and was highly specific to the PMI at which it existed. Its measurement and application are thus proposed instead of single-point thermometry, as it would be free of PMTP uncertainties.

Keywords — axial heat transfer, PMTP, axial thermal profile, antemortem central isotherm, single-point thermometry

I. INTRODUCTION

THE axial temperature distribution of a body at death – and not merely its core temperature alone – was shown to be an important predictor for the presence or absence of the postmortem temperature plateau (PMTP) phenomenon during subsequent postmortem cooling [1]. Empiric methods of death-time estimation such as the Cooling Formula [2] and Rectal Temperature Nomogram Method [3] – [6] apply only a body's single-point rectal temperature of 37°C assumed to have existed at death. Even numerical methods of death-time estimation that use 3D human computational phantoms to represent a dead body, such as the heatflow Finite Element Model [7] [8], do not approximate axial temperature distribution at death but instead focus on predicting a body core temperature of 37°C at death.

The PMTP is a period during postmortem cooling in which the core temperature as recorded by single-point thermometry remains constant for a variable time. The PMTP has special relevance to death-time estimation for several reasons. First, the postmortem temperature curve of a body's deep core has been known for a long time to be characterised by the PMTP as noted by multiple

authors [2], [4], [9] – [13]. Any mathematical method to estimate the death interval using body cooling had to include the body's PMTP value. Erstwhile rule-of-thumb methods of death-time estimation that did not include the PMTP [10] – [17] were thus deemed inadequate [18]. Death-time estimation methods that assigned a fixed PMTP value, e.g., 45 minutes [13], were similarly criticised [19] because the PMTP length was known to vary from one body to another. Some authors described instances in which bodies did not exhibit a PMTP [20] – [25].

The Cooling Formula adequately described postmortem rectal cooling and was expressed as:

$$\frac{T_r - T_a}{T_0 - T_a} = A \times \exp(B \times t) + (1 - A) \exp\left(\frac{A \times B}{A - B} \times t\right) \quad (1)$$

where T_r is rectal temperature at any time t , T_0 is the rectal temperature at death, T_a is ambient temperature, A is a constant, B is a constant, and t is the time of death. The second term, having the constant A in its exponent, represented the PMTP. Marshall [2] pointed out that using average values for constants in the Cooling Formula, including constants in the term that represent the PMTP, did not enable the time of death of a body found dead to

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be determined with a satisfactory degree of accuracy unless the constants were determined specifically for that body concerned. In other words, Cooling Formula constants that enable accurate death-time estimation were specific to a given body found dead and therefore needed to first be solved for before being applied to the Cooling Formula.

For the Cooling Formula to be practically usable, causes of the PMTP phenomenon in general needed to first be well understood, and methods to solve for all Cooling Formula constants needed to be described. Several authors offered a number of explanations for the PMTP. These included:

- 1) Gradual cessation of the calorific process/postmortem supravitality and decomposition playing a role in retarding cooling in the early postmortem period [10];
- 2) Postmortem heat generation by glycolysis in muscle over several hours [26];
- 3) Delayed cooling in the centre of the body until a temperature gradient was established from the body centre to the periphery [18];
- 4) A temperature gradient and body radius [12];
- 5) A small temperature gradient that exists at the core along with body radius [27];
- 6) Internal conductivity and thermal capacity of the human body retarding cooling of the core [28];
- 7) Anaerobic glycogenolysis, environmental temperature, surface insulation and body size [29],
- 8) Anaerobic respiration, cell lysis, chemical processes, bacterial activity, and rigor mortis [30]; and
- 9) That the PMTP was a random phenomenon that cannot be predicted due to differences in states such as core body temperature, hypothermia, drugs, trauma and biomarker concentration [31]. No consensus was reached on causes of the PMTP.

Meanwhile, empiric work by Henßge [3] established a strong correlation of the value of the Cooling Formula constant "A" with body mass to the power of -0.625 . Using that correlation and additional empiric work, Henßge described the Rectal Temperature Nomogram method of death-time estimation [4], which later applied body mass and corrective factors for postmortem cooling conditions that differed from standard conditions [6] [32], i.e. corrective factors for body coverings/clothing and for exposure to air/water flow. The Rectal Temperature Nomogram method became the accepted method of death-time estimation as it was relatively simple to use. By applying body mass and corrective factors, the Rectal Temperature Nomogram method appeared to acceptably negate the need to first solve for a given body's specific PMTP-value. The nomogram method reportedly had a 95% permissible variation of the estimated postmortem

interval (PMI) in hours and was verified in numerous subsequent studies.

None of the postulated mechanisms/causes of the PMTP translated to a method that solved for the PMTP value of a body found for the first time after death, as envisaged by Marshall in the application of the Cooling Formula. The significance of the study in Ref. [1] is that the PMTP appeared and disappeared in the same body whose core temperature was 37°C at death, an observation not previously described in the literature. The antemortem axial temperature distribution – and not core temperature – was the only variable that had been altered to create the effect. It was therefore inferred that the Cooling Formula's second term that describes the PMTP, or at least one of its constants, had to represent a body's antemortem axial temperature distribution.

The motivation for this study was to apply numerical analysis methods to understand the relationship between a body's antemortem axial temperature distribution at death and development of the PMTP phenomenon during subsequent postmortem cooling, a relationship that was empirically demonstrated in Ref. [1].

II. METHOD

The hypothetical scenario of death whose postmortem axial heat transfer was studied was that of a 34-year-old male marathon athlete who suddenly collapsed and died while training on a treadmill at a sports and exercise research facility. His jogging speed was 9 km/hr and body mass was 70.2kg. Room temperature before death had been set to 22°C via the air conditioner. His average power output recorded by the treadmill in the moments preceding death was 154W [33]. Room temperature setting was subsequently changed to 14°C immediately after he collapsed.

Step 1 – Approximation of antemortem axial temperature distribution

Numerical approximation of the body's antemortem axial temperature distribution was undertaken using materials and methods described in Ref. [34]. A 3D computational human phantom built from magnetic resonance images (MRI) of a living, healthy, 1.77m tall, 34-year-old male whose body mass was 70.2 kg was used as a human body surrogate. The phantom consisted of 247 anatomically segmented tissue domains. The Pennes BioHeat equation [35], normally expressed as:

$$\rho_t C_t \frac{\partial T_{ti}}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot (k_t \nabla T_{ti}) + \rho_b C_b \omega_b (T_b - T_{ti}) + Q_m \quad (2)$$

where ρ_t is density of a given tissue, C_t is the specific heat capacity of a given tissue, t is time, k_{ti} is thermal conductivity of a given tissue, ρ_{bl} is density of blood, C_{bl} is the specific heat capacity of blood, ω_b is the blood perfusion rate of a given tissue, T_b is the convective temperature of blood, T_{ti} is temperature of a given tissue and Q_m is the metabolic-heat generation rate of a given tissue, was applied to all its tissue domains using average ρ_t , k_{ti} and C_t parameters from the literature in a finite-element time-domain (FDTD) numerical analysis scheme. T_b was set to 37°C in all tissues. The Q_m sum of all tissues was equivalent to a total-body power output of 154W calculated from the 3D phantom's tissue masses. The initial condition was 37°C. A 'mixed' boundary condition type (Dirichlet plus Neumann) was used in which the heat transfer coefficient was 3.4 Wm⁻²C⁻¹ [36] and ambient air temperature was 22°C. Grid design and voxel creation were performed by the thermal solver's respective automated tools. The resultant grid consisted of 3.4595 x 10⁷ cells. The simulation interval was set to 9000s.

Step 2 – Numerical simulation of postmortem cooling to study axial heat transfer

Materials and methods applied in the numerical analysis of postmortem cooling were similar to those described in Step 1 and in Ref. [34]. The same 3D computational human phantom was used. For simplicity, the athlete was assumed to be naked, postmortem cooling was assumed to occur in natural/unforced convection conditions (no wind), and the body was assumed to not be in physical contact with solid objects. Average ρ_t , k_{ti} and C_t parameters from the literature [37] were applied. Q_m and ω_b parameters in eqn. (2) were assigned zero values to simulate death in all tissues. The antemortem axial temperature distribution approximated by Step 1 constituted the *initial condition* in this step. A 'mixed' boundary condition type (Dirichlet plus Neumann) was applied in which the heat transfer coefficient was set to 3.4 Wm⁻²C⁻¹ [36] and ambient air temperature set to 14°C. Grid design and voxel creation were performed using the respective automated thermal solver tools. The resultant grid consisted of 3.4595 x 10⁷ cells. The simulated postmortem cooling interval was 18000s (5 hours) and a 1-second time-step was applied. Simulation solutions were recorded every 180 seconds.

III. DISCUSSION

Assigning zero values to the Q_m and ω_b tissue parameters to simulate death reduced eqn. (2) to:

$$\rho_t C_t \frac{\partial T_{ti}}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot (k_t \nabla T_{ti}) \quad (3)$$

where:

$$\nabla = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \hat{i} + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \hat{j} + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \hat{k} \quad (4)$$

Eqn. (4) is written in 'strong' form as it holds in a point. To apply it in numerical analysis, it is cast into the 'weak' form by integrating over a volume V (e.g., a cube around a voxel):

$$\int \rho_t C_t \frac{\partial T_{ti}}{\partial t} dV = \int \nabla \cdot (k_t \nabla T_{ti}) dV \quad (5)$$

As V does not change in position or size during postmortem cooling, we can rewrite the left-hand side of eqn. (4) as:

$$\int \rho_t C_t \frac{\partial T_{ti}}{\partial t} dV = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int \rho_t C_t \frac{\partial T_{ti}}{\partial t} dV \quad (6)$$

For cell-centred finite-volume, all properties at cell centres can be further approximated as:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int \rho_t C_t \frac{\partial T_{ti}}{\partial t} dV \approx \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\rho_t C_t T_{ti}) V \quad (7)$$

for a specific voxel. Because ρ_t , k_{ti} and C_t remain constant during postmortem cooling, eqn. (7) can further be simplified to:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\rho_t C_t T_{ti}) V = \rho_t C_t \frac{\partial T_{ti}}{\partial t} V \quad (8)$$

where ρ_t and C_t have been removed from the temporal derivative. To deal with the spatial term, we looked at the 'weak' form by integrating over a volume V and applying the divergence theorem:

$$\int \nabla \cdot (k_t \nabla T_{ti}) dV = \int_A k_t \nabla T_{ti} \cdot n_\lambda dA \dots \quad (9)$$

where:

$$n_\lambda = n_x \hat{e}_x + n_y \hat{e}_y + n_z \hat{e}_z \quad (10)$$

is a unit vector normal to the surface A enclosing V :

Fig. 1. Indicating the relationship between volume V , surface area A and surface normal n_λ .

where A is the particular face segment of V , of which there are six for a voxel. Eqn. 9 can be expressed as:

$$\int_V \nabla \cdot (k_t \nabla T_{ti}) dV = \int_A Q dA \quad (11)$$

where Q is heat flux per square meter (W/m^2). There are two types of surface areas:

- a) A surface area between two voxel cubes, in which the heat flux can be expressed as:

$$Q = k_t \nabla T_{ti} \cdot n_\lambda = \frac{\partial T_{ti}}{\partial n_\lambda} \quad (12)$$

- b) A surface area that sits on the skin, in which the heat flux can be expressed as:

$$Q_c = h_c (T_{air} - T_{skin}) \quad (13)$$

or as:

$$Q_r = \sigma (T_{air}^4 - T_{skin}^4) \approx h_r (T_{air} - T_{skin}) \quad (14)$$

where Q_c is heat flux by thermal conduction, Q_r is heat flux by thermal radiation, h_c is the convective heat transfer coefficient, h_r is the radiative heat transfer coefficient, σ is the Stefan-Boltzmann constant ($5.670373 \times 10^{-8} \text{ Wm}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-4}$), T_{air} is temperature of the air in contact with the skin, and T_{skin} is temperature of the skin in contact with the air. Integrating eqns. (12) and (13) for convective heat transfer therefore gives:

$$Q_c = k_t \frac{\partial T_{ti}}{\partial n_\lambda} = h_c (T_{air} - T_{skin}) \quad (15)$$

and integrating eqns. (12) and (14) for radiative heat transfer gives:

$$Q_c = k_t \frac{\partial T_{ti}}{\partial n_\lambda} = h_r (T_{air} - T_{skin}) \quad (16)$$

When both convective and radiative heat transfer is present on the skin:

$$Q = (h_c + h_r)(T_{air} - T_{skin}) \quad (17)$$

which represents a mixed boundary condition if T_{skin} and Q are both specified.

IV. RESULTS

Step 1 – Approximated antemortem axial temperature distribution

The approximated antemortem axial temperature distribution was identical to that described in Ref. [34].

Step 2 – Postmortem axial heat transfer

The axial section selected to illustrate postmortem axial heat transfer was at the abdomen at the level of the liver, 1241mm from the lowest part of the 3D phantom's heel as indicated in Fig. 2. The following observations were made:

- At ± 180 s after death, an isotherm of 36.5°C previously confined to the skin in life had slightly thickened in its inner surface and pushed towards 37.4°C antemortem central isotherm (ACI) generally referred to as the 'hot core' during life, resulting in slight shrinkage of the ACI.
- At ± 360 s after death, a new isotherm of 36.3°C had developed on the outer surface of the skin. It surrounded and moved inwards towards the 36.5°C isotherm described earlier that had become circular. In turn, the 36.5°C isotherm had by this time further pushed inwards towards the 37.4°C ACI, causing the ACI to shrink further.
- At ± 2340 s after death, yet another new isotherm, this time of 36.1°C , had developed on the outer surface of the skin. It too surrounded and moved inwards towards the 36.3°C isotherm, which as a result moved inwards towards the 36.5°C isotherm, which as a result moved inwards towards the 37.4°C ACI, causing the ACI to shrink even further.
- This cycle was repeated a number of times. New and progressively cooler circular axial isotherms were created on the skin and gradually reduced in diameter as they propagated towards the body centre, while the diameter of the 37.4°C circular central antemortem isotherm simultaneously and gradually reduced.

- At 13860s (3hrs 51mins) after death, the 37.4°C ACI finally disappeared and the circular 36.5°C isotherm that had immediately surrounded it became the first 'postmortem' central isotherm. At the moment of birth, this postmortem central isotherm had a substantial radius. Like its antemortem counterpart, its diameter also gradually reduced as postmortem cooling continued to well beyond the 5-hour limit of the simulation, while at the same time progressively cooler isotherms continued to form at the skin.
- Axial sections in all other parts of the body, including the thighs and arms, also displayed propagating circular axial isotherms and shrinking central isotherms consistent with the described observations from the abdominal level. In the arms, the ACI lasted 1620s (27 minutes) in the left arm and 1980s (33 minutes) in the right arm before disappearing.

Fig. 2 Axial thermograms of the 3D phantom's abdomen recorded at different postmortem intervals and indicating shrinkage of the antemortem central isotherm and simultaneous formation of successively cooler isotherms at the skin.

Video 1 demonstrates the temporal evolution of axial isotherms during simulated postmortem cooling as described in the preceding paragraphs. One second of video playback represented 364s of simulated postmortem cooling. The 37.4°C ACI generally referred to as the 'hot

core' in life proved to be the PMTP if the ACI were to be recorded by single-point core thermometry, e.g. rectal thermometry. In this 3D human phantom, a thermometer tip placed at the centre of the ACI from death would measure 37.4°C for 3hr 51mins – which is the definition of its PMTP.

Video 1 An axial view of heat transfer in the chosen 3D computational human phantom demonstrating temporal evolution of isotherms during the simulated 5hr postmortem cooling interval. One second of playback represents 364s of postmortem cooling (hover the cursor over video and right-click to play).

The relationship between a body's antemortem axial temperature distribution and the PMTP sought by this study is that the length of a body's PMTP is directly proportional to the ratio of the ACI radius (r_{ACI}) to body radius (r_{body}) at the thermometry site at death, provided single-point thermometry was undertaken at the centre of the ACI and commenced at the moment of death. The ratio ranges from 0 to 1. The closer to 1 it is at death, the longer the PMTP will be, and vice versa. Absence of a PMTP in Ref. [1] was observed because only the body's core had been preheated to 37°C using a permanently fitted internal aquarium heater before death, while the rest of the body was cold. That had resulted in a ratio of almost zero at death. On the other hand, presence of the longest recorded PMTP in Ref. [1] was observed because the whole body had been preheated to 37°C in an incubator, which had resulted in a ratio of exactly 1.0 at death. All factors that affect the ratio may thus be regarded as additional Cooling Formula constants that predict PMTP length. Some of these factors include:

A. Antemortem physical exertion

Vigorous physical exertion produces excess body heat compared to the rested state, which is dissipated through the skin by cutaneous vasodilation and sweating while core body temperature is maintained within very narrow limits. The antemortem axial ratio of a body at death would be expected to differ depending on

the extent of antemortem physical exertion and subsequent thermoregulatory mechanisms deployed to cope with the excess heat so produced. The Step 1 simulation simulated jogging at 9km/hr, which had a power rating of 154W. Unfortunately, simulation of thermoregulation was beyond this study's materials and methods. Present-day methods of death-time estimation do not approximate a body's antemortem axial ratio that is the result of physical exertion and subsequent thermoregulation – they only approximate the antemortem core (rectal) temperature. This constitutes a source of uncertainty.

B. Skin thermal insulation

Thermal insulation by clothing/body coverings before death would result in the ACI extending towards the skin, i.e. skin temperature would be closer to deep core temperature. This would result in the ACI to body's axial cross section ratio at death to be close to 1.0, causing a longer PMTP. Therefore, clothing insulation could also be regarded as an additional Cooling Formula constant that predicts PMTP length. In this 3D computational phantom, clothing would have likely resulted in a PMTP longer than the recorded 3hrs 51mins. Present-day methods of death-time estimation do not approximate this ratio at death, but instead apply only an assumed single-point antemortem core temperature of 37°C. This constitutes a source of uncertainty.

C. Thermometry-depth

A single-point thermometer inserted into the 3D phantom in this study from the moment of death but midway between the body's centre and the skin would measure 37.4°C for a period shorter than the recorded 3hr 51mins. That is, a shorter PMTP would be recorded. Thus, axial thermometry-depth can be regarded as an additional Cooling Formula constant that predicts PMTP length. When considering death-time estimation, variations in relative thermometry-depth at a given interval after death could result in variation of the measured core temperature, which would then yield variations in subsequent death-time estimation calculations. The fact that axial thermometry-depth is not standardised by present-day methods of death-time estimation thus represents another source of uncertainty.

D. Body radius at thermometry site

The 37.4°C ACI's life span (the PMTP) was shorter in the arms due to their smaller radii compared to the abdomen radius. The 6-minute difference noted between PMTPs of the arms was thought to be the result of the 3D phantom's larger, presumably dominant right arm. Body radius constitutes the shortest linear distance of axial heat transfer from body centre to skin, the rate of which remains constant during postmortem cooling. Thus, a body's axial radius where thermometry is undertaken would be another Cooling Formula constant that predicts PMTP length, which is consistent with assertions by several authors [12] [27] [29], as stated earlier. The fact that body radius is not standardised by present-day methods of death-time estimation is thus another source of uncertainty.

E. The PMI at thermometry

Postmortem cooling is itself a natural method that reduces the r_{ACI}/r_{body} axial ratio from the moment of death, as demonstrated in this study. A single-point thermometer placed in the centre of the 3D phantom, but a number of minutes after death, say 1hr 30mins, would measure the 37.4°C ACI for the remaining 2hrs 21mins. The PMTP in that case would be 2hrs 21mins long. Thus, the time interval between death and thermometry – which for a body found dead is the PMI of that body to be ascertained – would be another Cooling Formula constant that predicts the PMTP length recorded by that thermometry. The longer the PMI before thermometry, the shorter would be the PMTP subsequently recorded. This is obviously a troubling and uncomfortable conclusion because the PMI of a body found dead is the unknown on the left-hand side of the equation which the Cooling Formula seeks to solve. It therefore cannot at the same time be an unknown constant predicting PMTP length that must first be known to be applied to the right-hand side the Cooling Formula. But evidently it is. This is an inescapable flaw of the Cooling Formula.

The fact that in this study Q_m and ω_b of all tissues were assigned zero values simultaneously before the simulation commenced indicated that no postmortem metabolism or any other biological phenomena were required to produce the PMTP, contrary to suggestions by several authors [10] [26] [29] [30]. Numerical simulation of the PMTP in this study did not require the application of a decrease-rate of internal power, as applied in the heatflow Finite Element

Model [7] [8]. This author was of the opinion that variations in the aforementioned factors were responsible for the apparent unpredictable nature and variations of PMTP length reported in the literature, which would explain difficulties in conclusive description of PMTP causes.

Single-point thermometry methods of death-time estimation evidently apply the isotherm temperature that exists at whatever body-depth is reached by the thermometer tip. Single-point thermometry cannot differentiate a large central isotherm existing earlier in the postmortem cooling interval from the same but smaller central isotherm that has shrunk in later parts of the cooling interval. Even present-day numerical methods of death-time estimation apply single-point rectal thermometry both for death-time estimation and validation. The study presented in this paper demonstrates that both the ACI and subsequent postmortem central isotherms exist for extended periods inside the body as their radii gradually reduce. Methods of death-time estimation that apply single-point core thermometry values that are based upon the Cooling Formula will suffer from PMTP-associated uncertainties as pointed out in this study.

The study presented in this paper demonstrates that the overall postmortem axial temperature profile of a body continuously changes from the moment of death, including during the period single-point core thermometry would perceive as the PMTP. This continuous change is highly specific to the number of minutes lapsed after death where a given axial temperature profile exists. It was this specificity that enabled axial heat transfer simulated in this study to be recoded in video format, where each image-frame depicted a specific postmortem axial temperature profile that corresponded to a specific number of minutes after death, and in which no two image-frames were duplicated throughout the cooling interval because of continuous cooling. This paper therefore proposes application of a body's measured postmortem axial temperature profile for death-time estimation instead of single-point thermometry. The proposed application would eliminate the need to solve for a body's PMTP (which requires a body's PMI to first be known) and would avoid uncertainties of single-point thermometry discussed in this paper.

V. CONCLUSION

The PMTP is chiefly a consequence of single-point thermometry of a body's ACI, which persists for several hours after death depending on its initial size and other

body and thermometry factors discussed previously. The temperature of a central isotherm measured after death using single-point thermometry is not specific to the cooling interval (PMI) at which it is measured. The postmortem axial profile of a body, on the other hand, has high specificity for the cooling interval at which it is measured. Its application in death-interval estimation is proposed to eliminate uncertainties arising from the PMTP and from single-point core thermometry. The proposed death-time estimation procedure that would apply a body's measured postmortem axial temperature profile would require priori approximation of the antemortem axial ratio, as already proposed in Ref. [34].

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